

DETERMINATION OF DOLUTEGRAVIR IN BULK AND ITS FORMULATION BY USING SIMPLE UV- SPECTROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

UV spectroscopic method was developed for the estimation of Dolutegravir in bulk and Formulation. The UV spectrum of Dolutegravir in methanol and water mixture showed λ max at 258nm. Beer's law is valid in the concentration range of 5-30 μ g/ml. This method was validated for linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD and LOQ. The method has demonstrated excellent linearity over the range of 5-30 μ g/ml with regression equation $y = 0.0446-0.0055$ and regression correlation coefficient $r^2 = 0.9997$. Moreover, the method was found to be highly sensitive with LOD (0.3602 μ g/ml) and LOQ (0.10915 μ g/ml). Depending on results the given method can be successfully applied for assay of Dolutegravir in formulation.

KEYWORDS: UV spectroscopy, λ max, Linearity, Standard deviation, Relative standard deviation.

INTRODUCTION

Dolutegravir is an antiretroviral drug widely used in the treatment of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection.

It belongs to the integrase strand transfer inhibitor (INSTI) class of drugs, which work by inhibiting the HIV integrase enzyme, thereby preventing viral replication. Due to its high efficacy, good tolerability, and once-daily dosing, dolutegravir has become an important

component in first-line antiretroviral therapy. Quality control of pharmaceutical drugs requires accurate, precise, and cost-effective analytical methods for the determination of the drug in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Among various analytical techniques, UV-Visible spectrophotometry is widely used because it is simple, rapid, economical, and does not require complex sample preparation. The present study aims to develop and validate a simple UV spectroscopic method for the determination of dolutegravir in bulk drug and its pharmaceutical formulations. The proposed method is based on the measurement of absorbance at a selected wavelength (λ_{\max}) and follows Beer-Lambert's law within a specific concentration range. This method can be successfully applied for routine quality control analysis in pharmaceutical laboratories.

Drug profile

Dolutegravir is a second-generation integrase strand transfer inhibitor widely used in the treatment of Human Immunodeficiency Virus type-1 (HIV-1). It exhibits potent antiviral activity, a high genetic barrier to resistance, favourable pharmacokinetics, and once-daily dosing. Because of its stability and strong UV absorbance, dolutegravir is frequently analyzed using UV-visible spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods in pharmaceutical research.

- **Structure of dolutegravir**

Fig. 1: Structure of dolutegravir.

- Chemical Name: (4R,12aS)-N-[(2,4-difluorophenyl)methyl]-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6,8-dioxo-3,4,6,8,12,12a-hexahydro-2H-pyrido[1',2':4,5]pyrazino[2,1-b][1,3]oxazine-9-carboxamide.
- Category: Anti-retroviral agent, HIV-1 Integrase strand transferase inhibitor.
- Molecular Formula: $C_{20}H_{19}F_2N_3O_5$
- Molecular Weight: 419.38g/mol
- pKa value: 8.2

- Brand: Tivicay (ViiV Healthcare), Triumeq (ViiV Healthcare), Juluca (ViiV Healthcare), Dovato (ViiV Healthcare), TLD (Tenofovir+Lamivudine+Dolutegravir).
- Pharmacokinetic Data Bioavailability-33%-66% Metabolism- metabolized in the liver by UGT1A1 through glucuronidation. A minor amount is metabolized by CYP3A4. The metabolites formed are pharmacologically inactive. Elimination half-life 12-15hours Maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) at approximately 1-3hours Excretion - feces (53%) and urine (31%).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemical and Reagent

- pharmaceutical grade dolutegravir standard was obtained as a gift sample. solvents like methanol, ethanol and distilled water are used.

Instruments

- UV- spectrophotometer: analytical (2080) Double beams UV-spectrophotometer.
- Sonicator: PCI Mumbai, Model No.3.5L 100H.
- Weighing balance: Shimadzu IN-201L and Analytical balance.

Selection of solvents

- The ability of solid substance (solute) to dissolve in solvent and to form a solution.
- The dolutegravir is soluble in methanol, ethanol and slightly soluble in water. Based on solubility of drug, methanol and water were selected as solvents.

Identification of Drug

Determination of melting point

The melting point of the dolutegravir was found to be in the range of 190–193°C with an average value of 191.6°C (average of 3 trails), indicating purity of the sample.

Selection of detection wavelength

- To determine the λ_{max} of dolutegravir 10 μ g/ml of working standard solution was scanned in UV wavelength range of 200-400nm using distilled water as a blank. It was observed that the drug shown maximum absorbance at 258nm.

Fig. 2: determination of λ_{max} .

Preparation of calibration curve

The calibration curve was plotted over a concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for dolutegravir by taking dolutegravir (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) stock solution 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 ml was shifted to a series of 10 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with methanol upto the mark. Calibration curve was prepared by taking readings at λ_{max} 258 nm and plotted a graph by taking the dolutegravir concentration on x axis and their representative absorbance on y axis calibration data

- From the absorbance values a calibration curve was plotted in the desired concentration range.
- The curve obtained was linear with correlation coefficient 0.9995 which represented.

Fig. 3: calibration curve of dolutegravir

Limit of Detection (LOD) And Limit of Quantification (LOQ) of Proposed Methods

Limit of Detection is the lowest concentration in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantified under the stated experimental conditions. The limit of quantitation is the lowest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be determined. LOD and LOQ were obtained from the slope and the standard deviation of the interception from three calibration curves determined by a linear regression line as defined by ICH. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification

(LOQ) were determined based on the standard deviation of the response and slope of the calibration curve. The method showed good linearity in six different concentration ranges with acceptable correlation coefficient (r^2 value).

Table 2: LOD and LOQ.

Linearity S.NO.	Slope	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	SD
1	0.0446	0.03602	0.10915	0.000477
2	0.0445			
3	0.04325			
4	0.0428			
5	0.0423			
6	0.0449			

Formulation Linearity

20 tablets of Dolutegravir (Tivicay-50mg) were weighed accurately and powdered by using mortar and pestle. The powder equivalent to 100mg of drug is taken into 100ml volumetric flask and add 3/4th volume of methanol. The solution is sonicated for 15mins and solution was made up to 100ml by using methanol. (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) solution was mixed well and filtered through whattman filter paper from the filtrate pipette out 10ml and make up to 100ml with water (working std) and the solution from the working standard pipette out 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 ml into a series of 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with water giving solution concentration 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared. The absorbance values of these were measured at 258nm.

Fig. 4: Linearity curve.

Accuracy and precision of proposed Methods

Accuracy

To check the accuracy of the developed method and to study interference of formulation excipients, analytical recovery studies were conducted by taking 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution of

formulation in each of three 10ml volumetric flask and then adding 0.5,1.0,1.5 ml of working standard Dolutegravir and make up to the mark with water. the solution was prepared in triplicate. The readings taken and the amount recovered calculated by using formula $Y=mx+c$ and the percentage recovery was calculated and given in the table 1.

Table 1: Recovery of dolutegravir.

Trails	Amount of drug present in ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	absorbance	Amount Recovery ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Percentage (%)	SD	RSD
1	15	5	0.8911	5.05	100.28	0.1722	0.1717
2	15	5	0.8895	5.02			
3	15	5	0.8901	5.03			
4	15	10	1.1101	9.97			
5	15	10	1.1152	10.08			
6	15	10	1.1139	10.05			
7	15	15	1.3325	14.95			
8	15	15	1.3339	14.98			
9	15	15	1.3354	15.01			

Precision

To check the precision of the proposed method the recovery studies performed three times on the same day (intra-day) and one time each day for three days (inter-day) were analysed. The relative standard deviation of intra-day and inter-day values were calculated. The precision is expressed in the form of percent relative standard deviation.

SUMMARY

A UV-Spectrophotometric method has been developed and validated for determination of Dolutegravir in bulk and its formulation. The process was done by using methanol as a solvent with the detection wavelength set at 258 nm. Dolutegravir was checked for its stability in the chosen solvent and found to be stable. The method was linear with correlation coefficient 0.9995 in the concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The limit detection and limit quantification were 0.03602 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.10915 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The intra day precisions are Percentage (%) = 100.203, Standard deviation (SD) =0.1915, Relative standard deviation (RSD) = 0.19103. The inter day precisions are Percentage (%) =100.17, Standard deviation (SD) =0.1742, Relative standard deviation (RSD) = 0.17423. The intra and inter-day precisions were satisfactory; the relative standard deviations did not exceed 2%. The accuracy of the method is high as can be seen from the mean recovery values of Dolutegravir

which were in the range of 5- 30 μ g/ml the method met the ICH regulatory requirements. The results of validation are summarized in the table no.3.

Table 3: Results.

SI. No	Parameter	Result
1	Detection of wavelength	258nm
2	Beer-Lamberts law (μ g/ml)	5-30 μ g/ml
3	Regression equation ($y=mx+c$)	0.0391
4	Slope	0.0437
5	Accuracy (% mean recovery)	100.03%
6	LOD	0.03602
7	LOQ	0.10915
8	Standard deviation	0.000477
9	Relative standard deviation	0.1717

CONCLUSION

A simple, novel, economical, rapid, precise, and accurate UV spectrophotometric method was developed for the estimation of Dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. The method was developed by using methanol as solvent. The developed method was validated for parameters via accuracy, precision, and linearity, limit of detection and limit of quantification as per ICH guidelines. All the parameters were found to be within the acceptance limits. The results indicated that the proposed method for the estimation of Dolutegravir is very accurate and cost effective and can be employed in routine sample analysis of Dolutegravir in bulk and its formulations.

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